

A Multiscale 3-D/1-D Multiphysics Molten Salt Reactor Simulation Framework Based on Moltres-SAM Coupling

Sun Myung Park^{1,*}, Cole A. Gentry¹, Nicholas Luciano¹, Kevin T. Clarno¹, Rok Krpan², Carlo Fiorina², Jean Ragusa²

¹The University of Texas at Austin, Austin, TX, USA; ²Texas A&M University, College Station, TX, USA

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803944

ABSTRACT

Molten Salt Reactor (MSR) analysis tools are critical for supporting MSR development and licensing. However, the circulating liquid fuel introduces unique computational challenges, including strong temperature reactivity feedback and the advection of delayed neutron precursors. This work introduces a coupled multiscale 3-D/1-D multiphysics framework for channel-type MSRs by linking two MOOSE-based codes: Moltres (neutronics) and SAM (thermal-hydraulics). This approach leverages computationally efficient system-level thermal-hydraulics while retaining channel-specific 3-D spatial resolution for precursor tracking and reactivity feedback in the core. We present the development and initial verification of this coupling using a quarter-core graphite-moderated MSR model. Steady-state results demonstrate that the coupled framework shows good agreement with analytical solutions and reference data. The developed framework provides a physics-based foundation to support ongoing data-driven digital twin development and enables comparative analyses against other multiphysics tools with differing model resolutions, such as the VERA simulation code suite and GeN-Foam multiphysics solver for reactor analysis.

Keywords: molten salt reactor, multiphysics, multiscale, MOOSE, MSRE

1. INTRODUCTION

MSRs have gained renewed interest as a promising Generation IV reactor concept due to their strongly negative reactivity feedback, high operating temperature, and potential for online fuel reprocessing. Unlike solid-fuel reactors, MSRs feature mobile fuel inventory, and the delayed neutron precursors (DNPs) drift with the circulating fuel salt. Therefore, the reactor kinetics are tightly coupled with thermal-hydraulics.

Developing reduced-order models for MSRs for digital twins or engineering-level tasks will require both experimental data and reliable simulation data from physics-based reactor analysis tools. Physics-based tools must demonstrate robustness and predictive capabilities over a wide range of MSR simulation scenarios to produce reliable training and reference data for reduced-order models. To that end, parallel efforts by the authors focus on code-to-code verification exercise between VERA [1] and GeN-Foam [2] through a series of MSR progression problems [3] based on the Molten Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE) reactor design. The VERA approach couples its high-fidelity 2-D Method of Characteristics (MOC)/1-D nodal P_N neutron transport solver MPACT to a system thermal-hydraulics code tailored for channel-type MSR analysis. GeN-Foam provides several multiphysics configuration options through a range of neutronics (neutron diffusion, SP_3 , and S_N) and computational fluid dynamics models.

In this work, we introduce a third multiphysics solver that bridges between the differing model fidelities of VERA and GeN-Foam for improved comparative analysis. It is a new multiscale 3-D/1-D

*sunmyung.park@austin.utexas.edu

multiphysics MSR analysis tool built by linking two Multiphysics Object-Oriented Simulation Environment (MOOSE) [4] applications: Moltres [5] and System Analysis Module (SAM) [6]. While Moltres itself is a multiphysics solver for MSRs with access to flow physics modules from the MOOSE framework, the Moltres-SAM coupling leverages SAM, an efficient nuclear system code supported by the Nuclear Energy Advanced Modeling and Simulation (NEAMS) program with specific features tailored for advanced reactor safety analysis. This tool also benefits from recent development work on Moltres for MSR analysis [7, 8, 9].

The 3-D/1-D approach couples a 3-D neutronics and solid heat conduction model in Moltres to a 1-D multichannel model in SAM. The multichannel model consists of a 1-to-1 ratio of 1-D pipes to the fuel channels in an MSR and the out-of-core components to form a closed salt loop including a pump and a heat exchanger. This contrasts with existing SAM models that either model the core as a single pipe [10] or a homogenized 2-D axisymmetric porous media region [11]. With almost 300 1-D components for a quarter-core MSR model, this work presents one of the largest channel-type models ever run in SAM. The primary goals of this study are to demonstrate the viability of the large multichannel models in SAM and perform initial verification of the Moltres-SAM coupling through pseudo-transient simulations for steady-state results of a quarter-core graphite-moderated MSR.

2. SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

2.1. MOLTRES

Moltres is an open-source multiphysics reactor simulation software developed for MSR modeling. Moltres solves the neutron diffusion or S_N neutron transport equations for neutronics modeling. The DNP model in Moltres supports coupling with any flow model in the MOOSE Navier-Stokes physics module. These modeling capabilities have been verified in code-to-code verification studies for MSR-specific phenomena [7, 8, 9].

Moltres has been used in past work to model the MSRE [5, 9], Molten Salt Fast Reactor (MSFR) [7], and fast-spectrum chloride MSRs [12]. A key factor for selecting Moltres for this work is its integration within the MOOSE ecosystem. As a MOOSE-based tool, Moltres benefits from highly scalable mesh and solver routines and ease of developing multiphysics coupling with SAM.

2.2. SYSTEM ANALYSIS MODULE (SAM)

SAM [6] is a modern system analysis tool for advanced reactor design optimization, safety analyses, and licensing support. SAM developers have implemented and tested several advanced features applicable to salt-cooled reactor analysis such as multiphase species transport, freeze plug modeling, and drift flux modeling. In most applications, SAM solves the 1-D weakly compressible flow equations along with heat transfer equations. The present work uses SAM-Lite, a non-export controlled version of SAM with some restricted capabilities removed. Since all capabilities demonstrated in this work can be replicated using SAM, we drop the *-Lite* suffix for brevity.

In general, two different SAM MSRE models have been demonstrated in the current literature. One SAM model approximated the MSRE core as a single 1-D pipe while preserving the height and flow area [10]. This model was validated against experimental data from various transient experiments by accurately reproducing integral neutronic and temperature metrics. The second SAM model coupled to the Griffin reactor physics code and modeled porous media flow in a homogenized 2-D axisymmetric MSRE model [11]. Both approaches modeled the ex-core salt loop using serially connected 1-D pipe regions forming a closed loop with the core region.

Figure 1. Moltres and SAM MultiApp coupling setup and data transfers.

2.3. MOLTRES-SAM COUPLING AND DATA TRANSFERS

Moltres-SAM multiphysics simulations couple Moltres and SAM as *sibling subapps* using the MOOSE MultiApp system. A *main app* dictates all data transfers between the two subapps but does not perform any calculations. Figure 1 shows an overview of how Moltres and SAM are coupled and the data transfers involved between the two codes.

Moltres solves the 3-D two-group neutron diffusion and graphite heat conduction equations and transfers neutron source distribution for precursor source calculations ($\sum_g \nu \Sigma_{f,g} \phi_g$), fission heat source distribution ($\sum_g \epsilon \Sigma_{f,g} \phi_g$), and graphite wall temperature distribution (T_{wall}) to SAM. These 3-D quantities are sampled and collapsed into 1-D distributions using `NearestPointLayeredAverage` and `NearestPointLayeredSideAverage` UserObjects before being transferred to corresponding 1-D regions in SAM.

SAM solves the 1-D multichannel thermal-hydraulics system and six-group precursor equations and transfers the fluid temperature distribution (T_{fluid}), wall heat transfer coefficient distribution (h_{wall}), and delayed neutron source distribution ($\sum_i \lambda_i C_i$) to Moltres. The data transfer process projects these distributions from each 1-D salt channel to the 3-D Moltres model. Consequently, the model sacrifices radial fidelity within each fuel channel. We expect this to have a small impact on local flux distributions and reactivity feedback but minimal impact on the overall distributions and feedbacks. These impacts will be investigated in future comparisons with GeN-Foam.

3. MODEL DESCRIPTION

3.1. MOLTEN SALT REACTOR MODEL SPECIFICATIONS

The MSR model is a preliminary design being developed for the MSR progression problems [3], a series of MSR benchmark problems to facilitate code-to-code verification between the Moltres-SAM tool, VERA [1], GeN-Foam, and other MSR software. The model incorporates most of the MSRE [13] design as a representative model of graphite-moderated MSRs. Several geometric approximations have been made to simplify model creation for code-to-code verification between multiphysics MSR analysis tools of varying model fidelity.

Figure 2a shows the MSR quarter-core geometry. It consists of 284 regular fuel channels and two central, annular salt half-channels. The fuel channel centroids form a $0.0508 \text{ m} \times 0.0508 \text{ m}$ square grid in the graphite matrix. These annular channels surround control rod thimbles which were omitted in this work due to incompatibility of the control rod and gas regions with the present neutron diffusion method. We plan to incorporate control rods in future studies. The present study also simplifies the peripheral core region by replacing the MSRE annular bypass channel, core can structure, and down-comer regions with graphite. We do not expect these approximations to have a significant impact on integral quantities, such as core inlet/outlet temperatures and the delayed neutron fraction, or point

Table I. Key specifications of the MSR core model.

Parameter	Value
Quarter-core power [MW]	2.0
Lower plenum height [m]	0.1875
Graphite height [m]	1.700 27
Upper plenum height [m]	0.254
Core radius [m]	0.7366
Annular channel inner radius [m]	0.0254
Annular channel outer radius [m]	0.031 992
Total mass flow rate [kg s ⁻¹]	37.289

 Table II. Salt and graphite material properties. T is temperature.

Property	Expression
Salt density [kg m ⁻³]	$2413 - (0.488 \times T)$
Salt viscosity [Pa s]	$1.16 \times 10^{-4} \times e^{(3755/T)}$
Salt heat capacity [J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	2386
Graphite density [kg m ⁻³]	1860
Graphite conductivity [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	154.797
Graphite heat capacity [J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	1758.46

quantities far from the peripheral regions, such as maximum salt and graphite temperatures. The fuel-graphite core region is sandwiched by the upper and lower plena regions filled with 100 % fuel salt and surrounded radially by a vessel wall. Table I lists key specifications of the MSR model. Table II lists salt and graphite material properties. Salt flows upwards through the core and flows through a pump and a heat exchanger before re-entering the core through a downcomer.

Figure 2. 3-D/1-D Moltres-SAM MSR geometries. The cutout shows the internal fuel channels in the 3-D model.

3.2. SIMULATION SETUP

Moltres models the 3-D core domain, while SAM models the primary salt loop as a closed 1-D flow loop, including 1-D pipes corresponding to each fuel channel and plena regions, as shown in Figures 2a and 2b, respectively. We applied form loss coefficients derived by [14]. Out-of-core SAM component specifications were taken from an existing SAM MSRE model [10] in the Virtual Test Bed Repository [15]. The 3-D Moltres model consisted of 5,932,325 degrees of freedom on 362,070 2nd-order 3-D mesh

elements. The 1-D SAM model consisted of 87,431 degrees of freedom on 4981 2nd-order 1-D mesh elements. Both meshes contained the same axial mesh resolution of 27 segments in the core region to ensure conservative data transfers.

Moltres applies monotone cubic interpolation on two-group material group constants generated using the OpenMC Monte Carlo particle transport simulations from 900 K to 1200 K at 100 K intervals.

The 3-D model applies a cosine gamma heat source, digitally sampled from Figure 14.2 of an MSRE report [16], in the graphite regions that is normalized to produce 7.8 % of total fission heat. Ideally, the MSR salt-graphite interfaces should have heat transfer coefficients that depend on local state variables to account for developing flow and internal heat generation. However, due to existing software constraints in SAM, the current model uses a constant heat transfer correlation for laminar flow ($Nu = 4.36$).

The 1-D SAM heat exchanger component is 2.5298-m long and contains a heat removal term of the form $[h(T(x) - T_s)]$ where $T(x)$ is the salt temperature and $T_s = 824.8$ K. We derived h analytically by defining the core inlet temperature $T_{in} = 908.15$ K and integrating across the 1-D heat exchanger region:

$$T_{out} = T_{in} + \frac{Q}{\dot{m}c_p} \quad (1)$$

$$h = \frac{\dot{m}c_p}{AL} \ln \frac{T_{out} - T_s}{T_{in} - T_s} \quad (2)$$

where \dot{m} is the mass flow rate, c_p is the specific heat capacity, A is the flow area, L is the length, and T_{out} is the core outlet temperature.

We ran a pseudo-transient simulation towards steady state by having Moltres execute steady-state k -eigenvalue neutron diffusion and heat conduction calculations while SAM-Lite executes transient thermal-hydraulics and DNP tracking calculations. Quarter-core power is fixed at 2 MW, equivalent to 8 MW full-core power. We set SAM-Lite to run multiple timesteps between steady-state Moltres calculations to accelerate the longest-lived DNP towards steady state. Timestep sizes for SAM-Lite started at 1 second and increased to 10 seconds by the end of the simulation. We used the steady-state results to run a tightly coupled null transient simulation using Picard iterations on 0.01-s timesteps to confirm that the system is at steady state.

For an effective delayed neutron fraction (β_{eff}) loss estimate at steady state, we ran another pseudo-transient simulation with stationary DNPs to isolate the impact of DNP flow while retaining thermal-hydraulic feedback. The reactivity difference between the two simulations provides the β_{eff} loss estimate.

The simulations ran with 256 MPI ranks on two AMD EPYC 9754 128-core processors. SAM-Lite ran on 16 MPI ranks to avoid excessive parallelization and limit its memory usage from replicated mesh storage. The Moltres subapp runs on a distributed memory mesh across all 256 MPI ranks. At the start of the simulations, when the reactor state is rapidly changing, each Moltres and SAM-Lite execution took approximately 1 minute and 0.5 minutes, respectively. Towards the end near steady state, execution times dropped to approximately 0.5 minutes and 5 seconds, respectively. Data transfers took 7 seconds from SAM to Moltres and less than 5 seconds from Moltres to SAM.

4. SIMULATION RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Figure 3 shows the steady-state temperature distributions in the 3-D graphite region and the 1-D fuel salt loop. The salt temperature peaks at the central core channel outlets as the salt advects heat out of the core. The two annular half-channels and two regular channels in the center report cooler salt temperatures arising from higher flow rates according to MSRE specifications. The graphite temperature peaks at just above the center of the graphite region due to the salt being hotter at the top of the core. The peak graphite temperature of 959 K is lower than the 976 K peak value computed by Haubenreich et al. [16] from a 10 MW MSRE model with an inlet temperature of 910 K. Assuming the temperature difference between the graphite central region and channel inlet scales linearly with reactor power going from 8 MW to 10 MW, the peak graphite temperature would be 973 K and in closer agreement with

the reference value.

The temperature difference between the inlet and outlet temperatures in Table III is consistent with analytical energy balance calculations for 2 MW power within 0.007 %. The average salt circulation time of 25.1 s is also consistent with analytical flow calculations from mass flow rates and loop geometry. These results verify that the model correctly conserves mass and energy within the primary loop, confirming the proper implementation of the Moltres-SAM coupling.

Since the MSR model has the same in-core residence and total recirculation times as the MSRE, β_{eff} loss due to DNP drift should be comparable to MSRE simulation results in existing literature. In Table III, the β_{eff} loss of 239 pcm agrees well with 242.8 pcm and 241 pcm losses reported by Jaradat et al. [11] and Shi & Fratoni [17]. The axial DNP production and decay distributions in Figure 4 agree qualitatively with the DNP distributions in the MSRE benchmark report [18] which reported 224.83 pcm loss. The unweighted β , calculated from a simple ratio of delayed neutrons to total neutrons produced in the core, corresponds to an unweighted β loss of 130 pcm. The 46% discrepancy between effective and unweighted β loss highlights the impact of DNP drift and delayed neutron production in regions of lower neutron importance in MSRs.

Figure 3. Graphite and fuel salt temperature distributions at steady-state.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work introduced a multiscale 3-D/1-D multiphysics simulation framework for channel-type MSR analysis by coupling Moltres to SAM through native MOOSE coupling interfaces. The multiscale approach leverages the computational efficiency of 1-D system-level thermal-hydraulics while retaining much of the 3-D spatial resolution in neutron flux, DNP, and temperature distributions.

We demonstrated and verified its capabilities through a steady-state simulation of a quarter-core MSR model derived heavily from the MSRE design. The 1-D multichannel model represents one of the largest SAM models ever run based on the number of pipes. The steady-state results agreed well with analytical energy balance calculations and reference MSRE data. Further verification work is ongoing to certify

Table III. Steady-state reactor results.

Parameter	Value
Inlet temperature [K]	908.15
Outlet temperature [K]	930.63
Maximum graphite temperature [K]	959.02
Maximum salt temperature [K]	943.52
Average salt circulation time [s]	25.1
Multiplication factor, k_{eff} [-]	1.063684
Multiplication factor with static DNP, $k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{static}}$ [-]	1.066391
Effective delayed neutron fraction loss, $\beta_{\text{eff}}^{\text{loss}}$ [pcm]	239
Unweighted delayed neutron fraction, β [pcm]	522

Figure 4. Total axial DNP production and decay distributions from Moltres-SAM.

that the Moltres-SAM coupling is consistent with other multiphysics tools in modeling MSRs through the MSR progression problem benchmarks [3]. Current efforts are also looking into optimizing performance to reduce computational costs.

Future efforts will incorporate control rod modeling and investigate asymmetric transients, such as blocked fuel channels and natural circulation events. Additionally, we will explore integrating this tool into a digital twin framework to generate training data and act as a digital shadow to reconstruct past incidents, forecast future behavior, and periodically recalibrate data-driven tools.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the State of Texas through the Digital Molten Salt Reactor Initiative. The authors acknowledge the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC) at The University of Texas at Austin for providing computational resources that have contributed to the research results reported within this paper. The authors thank the SAM development team at Argonne National Laboratory for their technical support.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. M. Graham, Z. Taylor, B. S. Collins, R. K. Salko, and M. Poschmann. "Multiphysics Coupling Methods for Molten Salt Reactor Modeling and Simulation in VERA." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 195**(10), pp. 1065–1086 (2021).
- [2] C. Fiorina. "The GeN-Foam multiphysics solver: a status update." In *Proceedings of the international conference on physics of reactors - PHYSOR 2022*, pp. 3164–3173 (2022).
- [3] C. A. Gentry, R. Krpan, K. Clarno, C. Fiorina, J. Ragusa, and B. Collins. "Graphite-Moderated Molten Salt Reactor Progression Problems." In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Mathematics and Computational Methods Applied to Nuclear Science and Engineering (M&C 2025)*. American Nuclear Society, Denver, CO (2025).
- [4] L. Harbour, G. Giudicelli, A. D. Lindsay, P. German, J. Hansel, C. Icenhour, M. Li, J. M. Miller, R. H. Stogner, P. Behne, D. Yankura, Z. M. Prince, C. DeChant, D. Schwen, B. W. Spencer, M. Tano, N. Choi, Y. Wang, M. Nezdyur, Y. Miao, T. Hu, S. Kumar, C. Matthews, B. Langley, N. Nobre, A. Blair, C. MacMackin, H. B. Rocha, E. Palmer, J. Carter, J. Meier, A. E. Slaughter, D. Andrš, R. W. Carlsen, F. Kong, D. R. Gaston, and C. J. Permann. "4.0 MOOSE: Enabling massively parallel Multiphysics simulation." *SoftwareX*, **volume 31**, p. 102264 (2025).

- [5] A. Lindsay, G. Ridley, A. Rykhlevskii, and K. Huff. "Introduction to Moltres: An application for simulation of Molten Salt Reactors." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 114**, pp. 530–540 (2018).
- [6] R. Hu, L. Zou, D. O'Grady, T. Mui, Z. J. Ooi, G. Hu, E. Cervi, G. Yang, D. Andrs, A. Lindsay, C. Permann, R. Salko, Q. Zhou, L. Fick, A. Heald, and H. Zhao. "SAM: A Modern System Code for Advanced Non-LWR Safety Analysis." *Nuclear Technology*, **volume 211**(9), pp. 1883–1902 (2025).
- [7] S. M. Park. *Advancement and Verification of Moltres for Molten Salt Reactor Safety Analysis*. Master's thesis, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, Urbana, IL (2020).
- [8] S. M. Park and M. Munk. "Verification of moltres for multiphysics simulations of fast-spectrum molten salt reactors." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 173**, p. 109111 (2022).
- [9] S. M. Park. *Advancements in moltres for time-dependent multiphysics molten salt reactor modeling*. Thesis, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign (2025).
- [10] R. Hu, G. Hu, M. Gorman, J. Fang, T. Mui, D. O'Grady, T. Fei, and R. Salko. "FY21 SAM Developments for MSR Modeling." Technical Report ANL/NSE-21/74, Argonne National Laboratory (2021).
- [11] M. K. Jaradat, J. Ortensi, G. Yang, R. Hu, and L. Zou. "Multiphysics Analysis of the MSRE Experiment Using Griffin-SAM Coupled Code System." Technical Report INL/CON-23-73281-Revision-1, Idaho National Laboratory, Idaho Falls, ID (2023).
- [12] K. Lawson and N. R. Brown. "Development of Two-Step Method for Fast Chloride MSR Neutronics." *Nuclear Technology*, **volume 210**(11), pp. 2133–2150 (2024).
- [13] R. C. Robertson. "MSRE DESIGN AND OPERATIONS REPORT. PART I. DESCRIPTION OF REACTOR DESIGN." Technical Report ORNL-TM-728, Oak Ridge National Lab., Tenn. (1965).
- [14] J. Faulkner. *Methodology for Multiphysics Modeling of the Molten Salt Reactor Experiment*. Ph.D. Dissertation, Georgia Institute of Technology, GA (2025).
- [15] G. L. Giudicelli, A. Abou-Jaoude, A. J. Novak, A. Abdelhameed, P. Balestra, L. Charlot, J. Fang, B. Feng, T. Folk, R. Freile, T. Freyman, D. Gaston, L. Harbour, T. Hua, W. Jiang, N. Martin, Y. Miao, J. Miller, I. Naupa, D. O'Grady, D. Reger, E. Shemon, N. Stauff, M. Tano, S. Terlizzi, S. Walker, and C. Permann. "The Virtual Test Bed (VTB) Repository: A Library of Reference Reactor Models Using NEAMS Tools." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 197**(8), pp. 2217–2233 (2023).
- [16] P. N. Haubenreich, J. R. Engel, B. E. Prince, and H. C. Claiborne. "Msre Design and Operations Report. Part Iii. Nuclear Analysis." Technical Report ORNL-TM-730, Oak Ridge National Lab., Tenn. (1964).
- [17] J. Shi and M. Fratoni. "GEN-FOAM MODEL AND BENCHMARK OF DELAYED NEUTRON PRECURSOR DRIFT IN THE MOLTEN SALT REACTOR EXPERIMENT." *EPJ Web of Conferences*, **volume 247**, p. 06040 (2021).
- [18] M. O. Fratoni, D. Shen, J. Powers, and G. Ilas. "Molten Salt Reactor Experiment Benchmark Evaluation." Technical Report DOE-UCB-8542, Univ. of California, Berkeley, CA (United States) (2020).